

Spontaneous Electrogravimetric Estimation of Rhenium

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Electrogravimetric estimation of rhenium was first reported by Lundell and Knowles¹. Tomicek and Tomicek² and recently Sen and Bandyopadhyay³ have improved the electro-analytical method. It has been observed by me that the gravimetric estimation of rhenium can be performed within a much shorter period with a fair accuracy using internal electrolysis method.

Reagents and Chemicals : The attackable anode used here was a pure tin rod of 7.50 mm of diameter (G.R.E. Mcrek variety). The Pt—gauze cathode used was of cylindrical type (diameter : 4.25 cm.). Potassium perrhenate used in the work was of 99.8 per cent purity supplied by Johnson Matthey and Co., which was further purified by recrystallisation from hot water. Other reagents used were of A.R. grade. The electrode was weighed before and after electrolysis on Bunge's microbalance.

Procedure : The electrolyte was a solution of standard potassium perrhenate in dilute sulphuric acid and optimum concentration of the acid was found to be 5% by volume. The volume of the electrolyte was 10 ml for each estimation. During electrolysis the anode was placed in the middle of the cell. The cathode and anode were short circuited with the help of a copper wire. The temperature of the solution was kept at 75 to 80°. The cathodic deposition was started within a minute which was first brownish, later metallic blue and finally black in color. To keep the deposited rhenium under the electrolyte, the level of the electrolyte was always maintained constant by adding water. At the end of deposition, a fresh 5 ml of 5% sulphuric acid solution was added in the cell and waited for a few minutes for complete deposition of the metal. The time required for each deposition was varied from 25 minutes to 100 minutes depending upon the amount of rhenium present in the solution. After the electrolysis the gauze was first rinsed with dilute sulphuric acid and then with distilled water and finally with acetone, quickly dried in air and then at 105° for 20 sec. The gauze was then cooled in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid for 15 minutes and weighed. The electrolyte after electrolysis was found to contain only traces of rhenium. The amount of potassium perrhenate was varied from an equivalent of 3 mgms. to 18 mgms. of rhenium.

1. Lundell and Knowles, *J. Res. Natl. Bur. Stds.*, 1937, **18**, 629.
2. Tomicek and Tomicek, *Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1939, **76**, 105.
3. B. K. Sen and P. Bandyopadhyay, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 709.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The electrode potentials for the systems $\text{Sn}^{+2} + 2e \rightleftharpoons \text{Sn}(s)$ and $\text{ReO}_4^- + 8\text{H}^+ + 7e \rightleftharpoons \text{Re}(s) + 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are -0.136V and $+0.36\text{V}$ respectively indicating sufficient difference between them for quantitative reaction. The driving force in this case is smaller than one volt, hence to obtain complete deposition in a reasonable time the resistance is minimised by using electrodes with a relatively large area. A higher temperature ($75-80^\circ$) is also required to further decrease the resistance. It is found that under the reducing environment of Sn^{+2} ion (produced during electrolysis) rhenium is not oxidised at this temperature. Electrolysis was also carried out at a temperature of $50-55^\circ$. The time required for depositoin of 5 mgms of rhenium at that temperature was about 6 hr. The electrodes like Zn/Zn^{2+} and $\text{Ag}/\text{AgI}(s)$, I are found to be unsuccessful. HCl cannot be used as an electrolyte because the deposition of metallic rhenium or dissolution of tin metal is very fast and a part of metallic rhenium is precipitated quickly without depositing on the gauze.

In total, 14 determinations were done, few analyses were given below :

TABLE

No. of experiment	mg. of Re in solution (taken)	mg. of cathode deposit	Time	Temperature
1	3.00	3.00	25 minutes	$75-80^\circ$
2	5.00	5.00	30-35 minutes	-do-
3	7.00	7.00	40-45 minutes	-do-
4	8.76	8.75	60 minutes	-do-
5	10.00	10.02	70-75 minutes	-do-
6	12.20	12.23	80 minutes	-do-
7	15.00	15.10	90 minutes	-do-
8	18.02	18.10	100 minutes	-do-

Further studies are in progress.

The author expresses his deep sense of gratitude to Prof. P. B. Sarkar and Dr. P. Bandyopadhyay for their kind suggestions and providing laboratory facilities. Thanks are also due to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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Received February 5, 1969

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